

A Comparative Study of Creativity of Senior Secondary Level Students Studying in Public and Central Schools

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Abstract— Creativity has been defined as a mental process involving the generation of new idea or concepts, or new associations between existing ideas or concepts. The study was intended to evaluate the creativity of senior secondary level students studying in Public and Central Schools. Sample of 60 students studying in Uttar Pradesh Higher Secondary Schools were taken for collection of data. The random sampling technique was employed. The paper concentrates on how creativity of students is associated with the type of school. It was concluded that there is no significant difference in all dimensions of creativity between Central and Public senior secondary school students.

Keywords: Creativity, Originality, Fluency, Flexibility

I. INTRODUCTION

Every day, we face new changes in all aspects of life and creativity is not only a means for adapting with changes but also a stimulus for producing knowledge in different fields of study. Education is defined as a process of developing the capabilities, abilities, knowledge and skills. Proper education, care and provision of different opportunities for creative expressions can inspire and sharpen the mind of individuals. Without proper education, training and opportunities for expression, all the talent is wasted. So, all the inherited abilities need stimulation and nourishment. In many educational institutions it has been observed that they provide very less opportunities to their students to develop critical and divergent thinking. There is no room for creativity or invention. It is believed that the school environment plays a very important part in encouraging students' creativity. The purpose of school is to serve as a hub where various activities can be organized to foster student creativity and inspire them to succeed in all aspects of life. However, if we examine the current system of education, we will discover that the majority of schools only focus on convergent thinking, maintaining discipline and obedience, and preparing students to learn in a way that will help them perform well on exams. This leads to rote learning, which is a significant problem. Additionally, it has been noted that pupils' creative abilities fluctuate depending on the type of school they attend nowadays. Besides school, the role of parents, members of the society, Government as well as the children themselves for proper nurturing and stimulation of the creative urge is very important. When creative potentialities would be properly developed and nurtured, it would ultimately play a significant role in getting better academic achievement.

II. NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Creativity refers to having inventive, productive and imaginative qualities. A creative person is able to link the existing information with new information in productive ways. Students who are creative may often be referred to as gifted or talented. Creative students, for example keenly observe a situation and have a desire to improve their abilities, produce variety of possible solutions to problem, are curious, original, comfortable with ambiguity, able to work independently, able to analyse and synthesise information, demonstrate compulsivity and an urgency to complete a task or execute an idea and have multiple talent abilities and characteristics of persistence. This study will investigate the differences in creative thinking among senior secondary students in **public and central schools**. This comparative analysis is needed to understand how different educational systems might influence the development of this critical skill.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study has been designed to achieve the following objectives

1. To find the fluency component of creativity of XIth grade students studying in Public and Central School.
2. To find the flexibility component of creativity of XIth grade students studying in Public and Central School.
3. To find the originality component of creativity of XIth grade students studying in Public and Central School.
4. To compare total creativity of XIth grade students studying in Public and Central school.

IV. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The following hypotheses have been formulated for the study:

1. There is no significant difference between fluency component of creativity of XIth grade students studying in Public and Central School.
2. There is no significant difference between flexibility component of creativity of XIth grade students studying in Public and Central School.
3. There is no significant difference between originality component of creativity of XIth grade students studying in Public and Central School.
4. There is no significant difference of total creativity of Public and Central school

V. RESEARCH METHOD

The present study has followed Normative Survey Method. After selection of title and tool, the data was collected from 60 students of higher secondary schools. The data thus collected were statistically analysed and conclusions were drawn.

V.I. SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

The sample is of small number of representative individuals from the population. This studying study is conducted on a sample of 60 students of XIth grade, 30 students studying in Public and 30 students studying in Central schools

V.II. TOOL USED

The researched used the verbal creativity test developed by Baqer Mehdi. This test has four activities. First three activities have three questions or problems, each problem related to three factors namely; fluency, flexibility and originality and last activity are descriptive type. Only 1 hour were given to administer it to the students.

V.III. STATISTICS TECHNIQUE USED

In this study random sampling technique has been adopted.

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis – 1

The hypothesis - 1 states as "There is no significant difference between fluency component of creativity of XI grade students belonging to Public and Central schools.

Mode of Institution	No. of Students	Mean	S.D.	Df 't' value
Central School	30	33.25	6.22	58
Public School	30	32.65	7.98	0.64

To test this hypothesis, 'There is no significant difference between the **fluency component of creativity** of XI grade students belonging to Public and Central schools,' the means and standard deviations of total creativity scores were computed separately for XI grade students of Central Schools and Public Schools. *t*-test was applied, which yielded a *t* value of **0.64** Since this obtained *t* value is lower than the critical value at the chosen level of significance, the difference was found to be statistically insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in the fluency component of creativity of XI grade students studying in Public and Central Schools.

Hypothesis - 2

The hypothesis 2 states "There is no significant difference between flexibility component of creativity of XIth grade students belonging to Central School and Public Schools.

Mode of Institution	No. of Students	Mean	S.D.	Df 't' value
Central School	30	20.65	3.96	58
Public School	30	19.90	4.47	0.93

To test this hypothesis, 'There is no significant difference between the **flexibility component of creativity** of XI grade students belonging to Public and Central schools,' the means and standard deviations of total creativity scores were computed separately for XI grade students of Central Schools and Public Schools. *t*-test was applied, which yielded a *t* value of **0.93**. Since this obtained *t* value is lower than the critical value at the chosen level of significance, the difference was found to be statistically insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in the flexibility component of creativity of XI grade students studying in Public and Central Schools.

Hypothesis – 3

The hypothesis - 3 states, "There is no significant difference between originality component of creativity of XIth grade students belonging to Central schools and Public schools".

Mode of Institution	No. of Students	Mean	S.D.	Df 't' value
Central School	30	8.30	3.14	58
Public School	30	5.10	3.42	0.85

To test this hypothesis, 'There is no significant difference between the **Originality component of creativity** of XI grade students belonging to Public and Central schools,' the means and standard deviations of total creativity scores were computed separately for XI grade students of Central Schools and Public Schools. *t*-test was applied, which yielded a *t* value of **0.85**. Since this obtained *t* value is lower than the critical value at the chosen level of significance, the difference was found to be statistically insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in the originality component of creativity of XI grade students studying in Public and Central Schools.

Hypothesis-4

The hypothesis 4 states, "There is no significant difference between total creativity of XIth grade students belonging to central Schools and Public Schools".

Mode of Institution	No. of Students	Mean	S.D.	Df 't' value
Central School	30	58.70	9.54	58
Public School	30	53.05	14.18	0.27

To test this hypothesis, 'There is no significant difference between the **total creativity** of XI grade students belonging to Public and Central schools,' the means and standard deviations of total creativity scores were computed separately for XI grade students

of Central Schools and Public Schools. t -test was applied, which yielded a t value of **0.27**. Since this obtained t value is lower than the critical value at the chosen level of significance, the difference was found to be statistically insignificant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in the total creativity of XI grade students studying in Public and Central Schools.

VII. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

On the basis of data analysis, findings suggest that the school type whether Public or Central, does not exert a significant influence on all aspects of creativity i.e. fluency, flexibility and originality among XI grade students.

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